

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

D9.2 - Monitoring & Evaluation Reports 1st release

22/07/2024

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Executive Summary

The present report describes the structure for the evaluation of the INNO4CFIs project quality and shows the assessment methods used and the results obtained. In particular, the results are based on the analysis of the 1st INNO4CFIs KoM and the 1st Internal Quality Assessment. Furthermore, this report shows the structure of the first two External Questionnaires (one dedicated to the INNO4CFIs Living Hubs and the second one to relevant actors in the WEFÉ-Nexus sector) that will be sent during next month (September 2024) to relevant stakeholders previously identified. Finally, next steps related to the INNO4CFIs quality evaluation have been described at the end of the present report.

1. Introduction

Quality Management consists of delineating the best strategy and methods the project will adopt to evaluate the pattern of the project in terms of the quality of the results obtained, the degree of satisfaction of the partners, and the involvement of potential stakeholders. In the INNO4CFIs project (where INNO4CFIs means “Nature-Based Business Model and Emerging Innovations to enhance Carbon Farming Initiatives (CFIs) while preserving Biodiversity, Water Security and Soil Health”) project, Quality Assurance is addressed in a fully dedicated Working Package - WP9, which is lead by CNR. The key goals of WP9 are:

- i) Facilitate the cooperation among partners,
- ii) Support rapid decision-making progress
- iii) Maintain strict control of gradual achievements of project objectives in terms of Quality

Moreover, a set of important objectives have been set for WP9:

- O.1 - Measure the INNO4CFIs **progress** through the duration of the project
- O.2 - Outline possible **improvement** in processes in cooperation with partners
- O.3 - Raise **awareness** about quality within the project
- O.4 - Support **identification** of quantitative and qualitative data

In particular, these WP9 objectives developed in three main Tasks that are here described:

- **Task 9.1 - Establishment of indicators and measuring tools**

This task, under the lead of ABCorporation plans to:

1. Develop the Quality Assurance Plan, the Monitoring and Evaluation Plan, and the Impact Assessment Plan
2. Develop assessment tools to monitor and evaluate partner meetings on overall project performance and progress, training events, cooperation, and networking between partners and external stakeholders, project results, and impact of each WP outcome. Project's results will be analysed according to several parameters: validity, relevance, appropriateness, usefulness, integrity, applicability, and impact. For the analysis, **standardised questionnaire surveys** (quantitative and qualitative) will be shared with the INNO4CFIs partners to express views, identify risks, and to make suggestions regarding changes and improvements based on four essential criteria: effectiveness, efficiency, relevance, impact, and sustainability.

- **Task 9.2 - Internal progress monitoring and continuous quality evaluation**

Under the guidance of IPSP-CNR, this task functions as an interim internal evaluation of the project quality, which will be performed using discussions during informal meetings, oral feedback, and self-evaluation questionnaires shared with the other partners after internal meetings and each General Assembly.

- **Task 9.3 - External quality assessment**

This last Task, also led by the IPSP-CNR, aims to perform an independent external quality assessment planned at mid-term and at the end of the project, which will assess the interest of potential stakeholders in the project outcomes. To this regard, the external quality assessment takes place at different project phases:

1. Preventive (in the first year of the project)
2. Advisory (after the first year of the project)
3. Control (after the end of the project - sustainability checks)

All the specific methodologies related to Quality Assurance in WP9 are described in the INNO4CFIs Quality Assurance Plan (QAP), which formalises the approach that will be adopted to maximise the quality of the project activities, outputs and outcomes, and project management.

The structure of the WP9 is furthermore composed of four different deliverables with subsequent deadlines, which are shown in table 1.

#	Title of expected deliverable	Type of expected deliverable	Due Date
<u>WP9: Quality</u>			
D9.1	Quality Assurance Plan	R — Document, report	M3
D9.2	Monitoring & Evaluation Reports – 1 st release	R — Document, report	M12
D9.3	Monitoring & Evaluation Reports – 2 nd release	R — Document, report	M24
D9.4	Monitoring & Evaluation Reports – Final release	R — Document, report	M36

TABLE 1. THE DELIVERABLES OF THE WP9

The monitoring performed by CNR involves the assessment of the following aspects of project implementation:

- **Relevance:** is the project still relevant in terms of its goals and achievements?
- **Efficiency:** are the activities in the different WP performed on time?
- **Effectiveness:** how well are the project-specific objectives met?
- **Impact:** at the level of departments, faculty, universities, etc.
- **Sustainability:** will the benefits last after the end of the project?

1.1 WP9 - The deliverable 9.2

The **Monitoring & Evaluation Reports - 1st release** is the second deliverable within WP9 of the INNO4CFIs project, following the elaboration of the QAP in M3.

The 1st release of the Monitoring & Evaluation Reports is expected to be elaborated at M12 of the INNO4CFIs project to evaluate the quality of the project by taking into consideration different important aspects. In particular, as foreseen by the QAP, an internal monitoring on quality and risk management was expected to be delivered within the first 6 months of the project. All the partners of the INNO4CFIs research project are required to contribute to the internal monitoring through several assessment methods, which include self-evaluation, Steering Committee meetings, and questionnaires/satisfaction surveys of target groups (e.g. participants of dissemination and training events).

The internal continuous monitoring, in cooperation with the coordination, ensures the implementation of the project as planned, achievement of objectives, provision of information on progress/delay activities, and determination of outputs & deliverables reached.

1.1.1 Quality assessment of the INNO4CFIs Project Kick-Off (K.O.) meeting

The INNO4CFIs Kick-Off (K.O.) meeting took place in Rome at Fondazione E. Amaldi Headquarters on 18-20th September 2023, in agreement with the European Commission representatives. The meeting was chaired by the appointed Project Coordinator (PC), Eleonora Lombardi, and attended by at least 1 member of each participating organisation in the project consortium and the EC Project Advisor, Pascale Gaucher, and EC DG REGIO representative, Eric Amaral-Garcia.

To evaluate the progress and the quality of the K.O. meeting, a self-evaluation questionnaire was prepared and shared with the Consortium partners after the meeting (only one questionnaire per partner was required). The K.O. the questionnaire was important for progressively improving the quality of future meetings. The integral text of the questionnaire has been added to the 1st release of the Monitoring & Evaluation Reports, before showing the relevant results.

Kick-Off Meeting (K.O.M.) evaluation

WP 9 Quality

In order to continually improve the quality of future meetings, please take the time to complete the following post-meeting evaluation. Your feedback is extremely valued! Thank you!

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. Did the kick-off meeting meet your expectations as a participants? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very Ineffective	Ineffective	Neutral	Effective	Very Effective
Objectives of the kick-off meeting	<input type="radio"/>				
Agenda	<input type="radio"/>				
Definition of the implementation strategy for the project	<input type="radio"/>				

3. Please provide any additional comments you have that relate to any of the above statements.

4. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. The FACILITATORS: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Demonstrated Objectivity	<input type="radio"/>				
Had excellent communication skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Displayed interest in the participants and in the process	<input type="radio"/>				
Ensured the participation and involvement of all participants	<input type="radio"/>				
Supported the mutual exchange and group learning from each other's communications	<input type="radio"/>				
Used the meeting time effectively	<input type="radio"/>				

5. Please provide any additional comments you have that relate to any of the above statements.

6. Please rate your OVERALL satisfaction with the MEETING.

Mark only one oval.

- Very Dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very Satisfied

7. Please provide any additional comments you have that relate to any of the above statements.

8. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The premises offered enough space for the type of meeting	<input type="radio"/>				
The organizer provided materials to support the implementation of the event (e.g. water, pens, pencils, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
The lunch options in the premises were satisfactory	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Please provide any additional comments you have that relate to any of the above statements.

10. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. *
LEISURE TIME:

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The "apericena" of the first evening met your expectations	<input type="radio"/>				
The social dinner of the second evening was satisfactory	<input type="radio"/>				
Overall, the leisure time was adequate considering the scope of the kick-off meeting	<input type="radio"/>				

11. Please provide any additional comments you have that relate to any of the above statements.

12. Please rate your overall satisfaction with the K.O.M. premise and leisure time.

Mark only one oval.

- Very Dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very Satisfied

13. Please provide any additional comments you have that relate to any of the above statements.

14. What recommendations do you have to improve FUTURE meetings?

15. Please describe any additional ideas or questions you have thought of since the meeting.

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1.1.1.1 Analysis of the results of the questionnaire on INNO4CFIs Project KoM

At the question **“Did the kick-off meeting meet your expectations as a participant?”**, 92% of the participants agreed on considering the objectives of the K.O. meeting as more than “effective” (of which 33% “effective” and 59% “very effective”). Regarding the Agenda of the K.O. meeting, 84% of the participants found it “effective” (of which 18% “effective” and 64% “very effective”). When considering the definition of the implementation strategy for the project, 75% of the participants found it “effective” (of which 25% “effective” and 50% very “effective”). These results are summarised in Fig.

1

Did the kick-off meeting meet your expectations as a participants?

FIGURE 1. LEVEL OF APPRECIATION OF THE K.O. MEETING OF THE PARTNERS

The partners also added additional suggestions for future K.O. meetings, which are reported below:

- K.O. future meetings should provide ample time and space to: develop a rapport with partners and individuals, discuss at length any confusion, gaps, and/or necessary changes to the GA, and understand key action points for the next several months. **All of this was achieved during the meeting**, but interactive activities to deeply dig into complex subjects could offer an additional advantage to the quality of future meetings.
- Future general meetings could provide each WP with enough time to ensure an ideal understanding of the other partners.

Moreover, the majority of the partners agree that the K.O. meeting organisers (or facilitators) demonstrated flexibility in adjusting the agenda when necessary and well-summarised key action points and problem areas, as shown in Fig. 2.

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. The FACILITATORS:

FIGURE 2. LEVEL OF APPRECIATION OF THE K.O. MEETING ORGANISATION OFFERED BY THE FACILITATORS

More generally, the majority of the participants declared to be "satisfied" (25%) or "very satisfied" (66.7%) with the K.O. meeting as shown in Fig. 3.

FIGURE 3. OVERALL SATISFACTION OF THE K.O. MEETING

At the possibility of giving more comments on the K.O meeting, a partner suggested shortening the timing of each WP presentation and expanding the space given interactive and workshop activities, which could improve the assessment of potential gaps and necessary amendments as well as build strong rapports between partners.

At the request for evaluation of the facilities provided by the K.O. meeting organisation, 75% of the partners agreed on the choice of location (Fig. 4).

FIGURE 4. LEVEL OF APPRECIATION OF THE LOCATION AND THE SERVICES OFFERED DURING THE K.O. MEETING

As additional suggestions for further improvements, some partners proposed to use round tables for better-integrating speakers and listeners. When evaluating the quality of the social activities during leisure time, partners showed overall great satisfaction (Fig. 5).

FIGURE 5. LEVEL OF APPRECIATION OF THE SOCIAL ACTIVITIES ORGANISED DURING THE K.O. MEETING

In the light of the previous suggestions, CNR, as leader of the WP9, proposed to the other partners of INNO4CFIs to organise the next General Assembly in the Italian Living Hub of Follonica, which has become the reference demo site of INNO4CFIs where all the technologies applied will be tested. This will offer the INNO4CFIs partners the opportunity to plan **interactive activities between partners at the agroforestry experimental plantation and will complement the General Assembly programme.**

Therefore, this will allow the partners to further develop connections and ideas, as also suggested by partners in the results of this questionnaire.

1.1.2 1st Internal Quality Questionnaire (M6- February 2024)

The monitoring of the quality and progress of the project is essential to evaluate the quality of the deliverables and how to identify potential gaps or future problems. Therefore, the first Internal Quality Questionnaire was developed in month 6 and shared with the INNO4CFIs partners for self-evaluation of the quality of the project.

To achieve complete and efficient results on Quality evaluation according to the Deming cycle PDCA driver, a standard methodology to review the outputs of the project activities was applied in the 1st Internal Questionnaire in February 2024. On this basis, the WP9 Quality team had the opportunity to assess the extent to which the commitments taken at the beginning of the project as well as five OECD-DAC criteria (**relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, sustainability, and impact**) are being met throughout the entire course of the project.

The guiding tools for the survey have been structured as follows:

- Activity 1: A thorough review of all the documents (milestones & deliverables) and other outputs produced by the INNO4CFIs project: the contents will be checked against the initial proposal (and thereafter according to amendments).
- Activity 2: Each WP leader and however partner will be interviewed using the interview guidelines attached as Annex 1 to this document.
- Activity 3: All the information collected as a result of the first two activities will be analysed in order to assess:
 - The compliance with the initial objectives;
 - The progress of the work against the indicators defined;
 - The extent to which the five evaluation criteria have been met.

For each one of these criteria, a structured report has been produced summarising the outcomes. More specifically:

- **Efficiency:** how well are resources being used?
 - **Definition:** The extent to which the intervention delivers, or is likely to deliver, results in an *economic* and *timely* way.

- **How is it evaluated:** through the analysis of the documents and of the interviews' outcomes, the coherence of the consumption of resources with the achieved outcomes and outputs has been assessed. This is a semi-quantitative assessment mostly based on the feedback by the partners (a detailed audit of the financial records is outside the scope of this review)
- **Effectiveness:** is the intervention achieving its objectives?
 - **Definition:** The extent to which the intervention achieved (or is expected to) its objectives and results, including any differential results across groups
 - **How it is evaluated:** The information collected through the analysis of the documentation and the interviews will be analysed to assess the level of attainment of the objectives and results, using the indicators provided in the proposal and specified in the monitoring plan. The following aspects will be evaluated:
 - a) Whether the indicators are still meaningful considering the possible evolution of the scenario;
 - b) Whether the quantitative targets set are still realistic;
 - c) The progress made, and whether it is in line with the expectations
- **The effectiveness and appropriateness of Quality management.**
- **Impact: what difference does the intervention make?**
 - **Definition:** The extent to which the intervention has generated or is expected to generate significant positive or negative, intended or unintended, higher-level effects.
 - **How is it evaluated:** the real impact can only be evaluated after the end of the project. However ongoing evaluations can be made of the extent to which the project has already produced a level of change for instance among the target groups which have participated in the project activities. This aspect will therefore be evaluated based on the indicators set in the proposal and on how they should be updated based on the activities carried out, on the analysis of the documents produced, and especially

of the surveys carried out after the communication and training campaigns, and finally as part of the interviews carried out with the partners.

- **Sustainability: will the benefits last?**

- **Definition:** The extent to which the net benefits of the intervention continue, or are likely to continue.
- **How is it evaluated:** the actual sustainability by definition can only be verified after the end of the funding phase, however at mid-term a number of aspects can be evaluated among which the will of the partners to implement the sustainability measures envisaged in the proposal and the commitment to replicate and to carry on the project's results;

- **Relevance: is the intervention doing the right things?**

- **Definition:** The extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries', global, country, and partner/institution needs, policies, and priorities, and continue to do so if circumstances change.
- **How is it evaluated:** the INNO4CFIs project proposal was designed in 2022, and it identified a set of issues to be addressed, described in a high level of detail in the proposal itself. One and a half year later, the context might have changed (especially that of C farming which is being legislated at the European level) and therefore it is important to verify that the objectives and expected results of the project are still in line with the identified needs. This can only be done through an interactive session with the partners, and especially with relevant stakeholders, to verify that the action is still adherent to the society and market needs and in case of significant modifications, to formulate suggestions for improvement.

As the 1st Amendment was still in the process of official approval and many Deliverables and Milestones have been rescheduled, some project activities were in the detailed planned stage while external stakeholders are still being precisely defined. Consequently, **the 1st Quality Internal questionnaire has been developed in a shortened form taking into consideration only a few aspects that can be properly**

evaluated. Therefore, the last two OECD-DAC criteria (Impact, Sustainability) were not included in the 1st Internal Quality Questionnaire.

To progressively and efficiently assess the quality of the INNO4CFIs project, the Internal Quality Questionnaire will be repeated every 12 months and the results will constitute an essential part of the Monitoring & Evaluation Reports (scheduled at M18 and M30). This will avoid overlapping with the General Assemblies, which will be followed by a specific quality questionnaire. The text of the 1st Internal Questionnaire is hereafter included.

Annex 1: Internal Questionnaire

Name of the organisation:

Name of the Responsible for Quality:

Evaluation criteria: EFFICIENCY

- **Efficiency: how well are resources being used?**
 - **Definition:** The extent to which the intervention delivers, or is likely to deliver, results in an economic and timely way.

Question 1: Please rate (%) the extent to which the project's expenditure is in line with the scheduled value.

Answer:

Question 2: Are there significant deviations?

Answer:

Question 3: If yes, which ones?

Answer:

Question 4: Please illustrate the eventual recovery actions, i.e. what do you plan to do to bring the situation back on track?

Answer:

Question 5: Do you still consider that the initial budget forecast is correct?

Answer:

Question 6: Do you think a reallocation of budget/resources is needed? If yes, of what nature?

Answer:

Question 7: Were objectives achieved on time?

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Answer:

Evaluation criteria: EFFECTIVENESS

- **Effectiveness: is the intervention achieving its objectives?**
 - **Definition:** The extent to which the intervention achieved, or is expected to achieve, its objectives, and its results, including any differential results across groups.

Question 9: Has the Deliverable and Milestones list been updated (rescheduled) during the first 6 months of the project's lifetime? If yes, how?

Answer:

In the proposal, a number of indicators (KPI) have been defined.

Question 10: Do you think that these indicators are still valid, or should they be modified? If yes, how?

Answer:

Question 11: What is the progress of the project in terms of the current value of the indicators?

Answer:

Question 12: Is the management of the project and the management of the project quality being carried out as expected? Should they be modified? If Yes, how?

Answer:

Question 13: Is the risk analysis set out at the beginning of the action still valid? If not, why?

Answer:

Question 14: Are there new, unforeseen risks to be dealt with? If yes, which ones?

Answer:

Question 15: Has it been necessary to deploy some of the risk mitigation measures? Have they been effective?

Answer:

Question 16: What were/are the major factors influencing the achievement or non-achievement of the objectives?

Answer:

Evaluation criteria: RELEVANCE

- **Relevance: is the intervention doing the right things?**
 - **Definition:** The extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries', global, country, and partner/institution needs, policies, and priorities, and continue to do so if circumstances change.

Question 17: The INNO4CFIs project proposal was designed during 2022, and it identified a set of issues to be addressed, described in the proposal itself. One and a half year later, has the context changed, and therefore, are the objectives and expected results of the project still in line with the identified needs?

Answer:

Question 18: If not, can you formulate suggestions for improvement, thus maintaining or increasing the relevance of the action?

Answer:

Question 19: Are there any other comments on any aspect of the project which you would like to make?

Answer:

1.1.2.1 Analysis of the results of the 1st Internal Quality Questionnaire (M6- February 2024)

The analysis of the results of the 1st Internal Quality Questionnaire is essential to correctly and efficiently manage the internal quality of the INNO4CFIs project. Hereafter, the results for the different quality criteria that have been assessed are shown.

Efficiency

The adoption of the Efficiency criteria is functional to assess how well the resources of INNO4CFIs are used. In other words, Efficiency measures the extent to which the intervention delivers, or is likely to deliver, results in an economic and timely way. Eight key aspects regarding efficiency were analysed in the Questionnaire, whose results are reported here.

First of all, all the Consortium partners were asked to **evaluate the extent to which the project's expenditure is in line with the scheduled value**. The majority of the partners (66,6%) declared that the current project expenditure is at least 90% in line with the scheduled value (Fig. 6).

FIGURE 6. ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT PROJECT'S EXPENDITURE AS COMPARED WITH THE SCHEDULED VALUE

This results means that the initial value was efficiently planned. When asked **if the deviations from the scheduled value were significant**, half of the partners (50%) declared it significant (Fig. 7).

FIGURE 7. PERCENTAGE OF SIGNIFICANT DEVIATIONS IN THE PROJECT EXPENDITURE FROM THE SCHEDULED VALUE

Such deviations, which have been already included in the 2nd Amendment, derived from unforeseen costs that are reported in Table 2:

Reasons for significant deviations in the project's expenditure	Eventual recovery actions
Increased agroforestry plantation costs	Research of more economical solutions
Increased communication activities	Meeting timing will be increased
Higher technology implementation costs	Budget reallocation in the 2nd Amendment
Higher management costs of the INNO4CFIs Living Hubs	Budget reallocation in the 2nd Amendment
Partial reallocation of the budget for drone flights due to rescheduling in biomass measurements activities	No increase in budget costs

TABLE 2. EXPLANATION FOR THE SIGNIFICANT DEVIATION IN PROJECT EXPENDITURE

In light of some significant deviations in project expenditure, partners **were required to assess the validity of the initial budget**. 83,3% of the partners answered that the initial budget of the INNO4CFIs project is correct (Fig. 8). Some partners reported the initial budget as not completely fulfilling the requirements as unforeseen costs occurred during the realisation of the agroforestry systems. Moreover, higher costs than expected were found over demosite technology installation, especially in travel costs. In regard to the unforeseen costs, 41,6% of the partners declared to have required a reallocation of the budget in the 2nd amendment (Fig. 9)

FIGURE 8 AND 9. ASSESSMENT OF THE VALIDITY OF THE INITIAL BUDGET AND OF BUDGET REALLOCATION

Given the difficulties encountered in the activities of some of the WP, **the analysis of achievements of the project objectives on time is essential for the evaluation of**

project quality and management. To this regard, 75% of the Consortium partners answered they achieved their objectives on time (Fig. 10). When it was not the case, partners specified that it was due to specific WP conditions (i.e. activities starting later as compared with others) or to a not proper setting of deliverables and milestones (corrected in the 1st Amendment).

FIGURE 10. ASSESSMENT OF THE ACHIEVEMENT OF THE PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Effectiveness

The assessment of the project’s effectiveness measures the extent to which the intervention achieved, or is expected to, its objectives, and its results, including any differential results across groups. In other words, this parameter aims to evaluate if the intervention is achieving its objectives.

The work plan of the INNO4CFIs project defines milestones and the acceptance criteria for each phase of the project. In particular, quality control of INNO4CFIs sets a monitoring and review of milestones/deliverables and requires deliverables/periodic reports to EC. To this regard, the monitoring of the achievement of the planned deliverables and milestones through self-evaluation methods by the partners is of the essence. Therefore, each single partner of the INNO4CFIs Consortium regularly verifies the status of the milestones and deliverables of their WP. A review of all the deliverables and milestone status was performed in the present Internal Quality Questionnaire in collaboration with the coordination. In the first six months of the INNO4CFIs project, 66.6% of the partners reported a rescheduling of milestones and

deliverables (Fig. 11), whose some of the changes are reported in Table 3. The updates are well explained in the text of the 2nd amendment.

FIGURE 11. SELF-EVALUATION OF THE UPDATES BROUGHT TO THE LIST OF DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES

Updates brought to the list of Deliverables and Milestones of INNO4CFIs
Deliverable D4.1 rescheduled from M6 to M12
Data model DLT postponed to M8
D3.2 rescheduled from M12 to M18 for optimal task's alignment

TABLE 3. SOME OF THE CHANGES BROUGHT TO THE LIST OF THE INNO4CFIs DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES BY THE PARTNERS AS AN EXAMPLE

Moreover, the second key objective of the INNO4CFIs project assessment is the constant measurement, interpretation and display of relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). A list of the KPIs and monitored indicators throughout the project is available in the Quality Assurance Plan. To guarantee the transparent display of the KPIs to the Consortium, internal evaluation reports, based on the procedures and templates are contrived on a regular basis. The 1st Internal Quality Questionnaire assessed the current validity of the KPI list in the INNO4CFIs project. 75% of the INNO4CFIs partners agree on not modifying the list of the KPIs (Fig. 12).

FIGURE 12. ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT VALIDITY OF THE INNO4CFIS KPI LIST

Any modification of the KPI has already been included in the 2nd amendment. Overall, partners additionally suggested they should be modified according to the needs of the project, after discussion with relevant partners in specific tasks. Furthermore, partners proposed to keep the KPI list constantly monitored and updated, especially after the onboarding of new partners. The monitoring of the progress of the project in terms of adherence to the KPIs is an efficient way to evaluate the quality of the project. When required to assess the progress of the project in terms of the current value of the indicators, 75% of the partners expressed satisfaction by describing the WP activities on track (Fig. 13). The other partners specified that their WP-specific activities have just started and therefore are in a planned preliminary phase, which will become completely operative during next months.

FIGURE 12. ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT PROGRESS OF THE PROJECT ACCORDING TO THE VALUES OF THE INDICATORS

In parallel to the analysis of the progress of the project, the 1st Internal Quality Questionnaire assessed the degree of satisfaction of the partners with the management of the project and the monitoring of the quality. In particular, partners were proposed to give any suggestion on how to improve these two important aspects. Overall, the partners expressed great satisfaction both with the project management and the quality management (Fig. 13). Interestingly, some partners proposed to maximise the efficiency of the activities by reducing the number of monthly meetings to half (i.e. every two months). This could offer partners more time for collecting results and assessing the work of the other WPs. This suggestion has been taken into consideration by the Project Coordination and potentially accepted after the official approval of the 2nd Amendment and only if the internal and external factors will allow it. Moreover, another suggestion proposed to introduce additional monthly meetings between task leaders about the management of the demo sites.

FIGURE 13. ASSESSMENT OF PROJECT'S MANAGEMENT AND QUALITY BY THE INNO4CFIS PARTNERS

The risk management strategy targets issues that could potentially threaten the achievement of the overall goal of the project and its objectives. It considers any potential financial risks (overspending or underspending), timing (postponing of activities/deliverables and sustainability of the project results). The identification and assessment of new risks is a joint responsibility of all the project partners, who have to inform the Project Coordinator and the Steering Committee about any possible intervention or solution. In particular, partners might suggest preventive measures (avoiding the risk that occurs) and corrective actions (decreasing the severity and impact).

The 1st Internal Quality Questionnaire was the first self-evaluation analysis by the partners to identify potential new risks in the project. The majority of the partners (75%) believes that the initial risk analysis can still efficiently address potential new risks (Fig. 14).

FIGURE 14. ASSESSMENT OF THE VALIDITY OF THE INITIAL RISK ANALYSIS

The partners offered useful suggestions for improving the initial risk analysis, which are reported in Table 4:

Suggestions for improvement of the initial risk analysis
1. The risk analysis could be updated yearly to efficiently identify new risks
2. New mitigation strategies could be collected in a non-official deliverable and stored in a project folder
3. The initial risk analysis should be continuously evaluated based on the specific period of the project

TABLE 4. SUGGESTIONS FROM THE PARTNERS FOR IMPROVING THE INITIAL RISK ANALYSIS

The partners were also asked to try to identify unforeseen risks that the project might deal with. Partners suggested focusing on the risks of the lack of information on carbon credits (CC) at the European level, the effort of onboarding new partners and finally a potential delay in the approval of the 2nd amendment, which could slow the implementation of the INNO4CFIs Carbon Farming Technology.

When considering the necessity of mitigation measurements, the majority of the partners (75%) did not express a request for mitigation measurements (Fig. 15).

FIGURE 15. PARTNERS' CONSIDERATION ABOUT THE NECESSITY OF MITIGATION MEASUREMENTS

However, particular attention was proposed on the following aspects:

- The need of stakeholders that are involved in the Carbon Credit market
- The presence of professional with specific skills
- The 2nd Amendment contains a plan that mitigates the foreseen delays in the delivery of deliverables and milestones.

The achievement of the objectives of the INNO4CFIs project could be hampered by several factors. The partners were asked to identify potential factors influencing the achievement, which are summarised in the categories shown in Fig. 16.

What are the factors influencing the achievement of the objectives?

FIGURE 16. IDENTIFICATION OF NEW UNFORESEEN RISKS SUMMARISED INTO CATEGORIES

In particular, partners put attention to:

- The ability of the INNO4CFIs Consortium to economically and functionally integrate the different technologies in a scalable and sustainable solution so that it is adapted to different contexts.
- An efficient collaboration and clear communication between the INNO4CFIs partners.
- The possibility of collecting field data with good weather conditions (availability of cloud-free satellite imagery, good UAV data).
- The reallocation of the budget while keeping an attractive financing budget.

Relevance

Relevance measures the extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries, global, national, and partner/institution needs, policies, priorities and continue to do so if circumstances change. Alternatively, efficiency try to answer a very basic question: "Is the intervention doing the right things?".

This question is of increasing importance as time is passing from when the INNO4CFIs initial proposal was designed in 2022. After two years, the INNO4CFIs were asked if the context changed and the project objectives and expected results are still in line with the identified needs. Despite the time passed so far, the majority of the partners

83% agreed on the current validity of the project objectives and proposal (Fig. 17).

FIGURE 17. ANALYSIS OF THE ACTUAL VALIDITY OF PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND PROPOSAL

When asked to give suggestions for improvements, the partners focused on two main aspects:

1. Constantly monitoring the future regulation of Carbon Farming at the European level (currently under discussion) and the market dynamics of carbon credits. This approach could progressively validate the validity of the INNO4CFIs consortium business proposal throughout the entire course of the project.
2. Onboarding new partners for other innovative technologies to be applied in the INNO4CFIs project could further enhance the innovation rate of the project.

1.1.3 External Quality Monitoring (M12)

The External Monitoring of quality, under the lead of CNR, focuses on developing an independent external quality assessment of the interest potential stakeholders have in the outcomes of the INNO4CFIs project. The analysis of the impact and relevance of the INNO4CFIs on society is of primary importance.

After preliminary discussions with ABCorporation, CNR proposed to divide the External Monitoring in two main quality questionnaires to better monitor the interest of stakeholders:

- A first external quality questionnaire that aims to evaluate the impact the INNO4CFIs Living Hubs (LHs) have in involving potential stakeholders at a broader level. In particular, this approach will offer the INNO4CFIs quality team the opportunity to understand how concepts such as “carbon farming”, “agroforestry” etc. are known and interesting at a broader society level. To better facilitate the sharing with local stakeholders, this first questionnaire will be translated into the respective national languages by the partners directly involved in the management of each LH.
- A second external quality questionnaire aiming to assess the level of innovation of INNO4CFIs in the WEFÉ-Nexus approach by the analysis of previous European WEFÉ-NEXus and carbon farming-related projects. Based on the work performed by the WP2, this second external questionnaire is targeting key coordinators in this sector.

Both the two questionnaires have been already developed in strict collaboration with ABCorporation and will be shared using Google Form with interested stakeholders by the end of M12 (September 2024). A list of potential stakeholders will be created according to the suggestions from the WP10 - Dissemination and Sustainability - under the lead of the partner ABCorporation. This list will be then collected and saved in a project folder. The analysis of the results will offer qualitative and quantitative data on the external impact of the INNO4CFIs project to date.

1.1.3.1 The stakeholders questionnaire on the INNO4CFIs Living Hubs

This first questionnaire aims to assess the impact of the INNO4CFIs Living Hubs on the involvement of potential stakeholders through 8 essential questions. The structure has been maintained as simple as to be comprehensible at a broader level.

The integral text of this first questionnaire is hereafter added.

INNO4CFIs

Stakeholders Questionnaire on the INNO4CFIs Living Hubs

INNO4CFIs - Business model for "**Nature-Based Business Model and Emerging INNOvations to enhance Carbon Farming Initiatives (CFIs) while preserving Biodiversity, Water Security and Soil Health**" - is a project co-funded by the I3 Instrument as part of the European Regional and Development Fund.

[INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming](#)

The project aims to promote carbon farming (CF) business models using nature-based innovative technologies that enhance CO₂ sequestration while producing vital environmental benefits such as freshwater production, soil restoration and biodiversity promotion. Focusing on CF and reforestation initiatives, INNO4CFIs pursues the development of a Carbon Technology Platform that revolutionises CF and creates a highly replicable and scalable business model.

Realised in 4 European Living Hubs (LHs), INNO4CFIs is integrating highly innovative solutions such as a desalination technology, mycoproducts production, and satellite analyses while financing other green solutions through a cascade funding scheme for the promotion of resilience and competitiveness in the European regions.

The INNO4CFIs Consortium, coordinated by the E. Amaldi Foundation, is composed of 14 partners that represent the innovation ecosystem in 13 different regions of 8 European countries (IT, GR, SP, BE, NL, IE, AT, DE).

To completely and accurately assess the impact of the INNO4CFIs LHs on involving potentially interested local stakeholders, we prepared the present questionnaire that contains 8 questions addressing key aspects of INNO4CFIs and their impacts on the pre-fixed objectives.

Keywords: Nature-based solutions (NBS), Agroforestry, Carbon Farming (CF), Tree carbon sequestration, solar-powered seawater desalination, agroforestry biodiversity, EU Regulamentation on carbon credits.

- 1. **Nature-based solutions (NbS)** consist of actions that protect, sustainably manage and restore natural or modified ecosystems (ex. arable fields) and that address challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing benefits for human well-being and biodiversity.

In agriculture, NbS means natural processes relying on ecosystems functioning to ensure food and livelihood security, healthier diets and more inclusive rural economies.

Do you think NBS offer an innovative contribution to the agricultural and forestry sectors?

Please answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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2. **Agroforestry.** Climate change threatens traditional agricultural and forestry systems by reducing primary crop production and their associated ecosystem services. Agroforestry is a landscape management approach that offers relevant benefits. Planting trees, shrubs and hedges in traditional agricultural fields can enhance soil health and sustain crop productivity thanks to higher protection from abiotic stresses exacerbated by climate change. Moreover, agroforestry also increases biodiversity by developing vital habitats for the wild fauna.

Do you think agroforestry can innovatively contribute to sustainability and resilience to climate change?

Please answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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3. **Carbon farming (CF) for CO₂ sequestration.** Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions have already reached record levels and are dramatically impeding progress to limit climate change. Therefore, reaching climate goals requires strategies that actively remove CO₂ from the atmosphere. Carbon farming is a range of agricultural methods that aim to sequester CO₂ into plant and soil biomass

Do you think agroforestry-based CF initiatives can significantly contribute to the reduction of atmospheric CO₂?

Please answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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4. **Measurement of tree carbon sequestration:** quantifying tree carbon sequestration traditionally requires tree biomass destructive measurements that are expensive, time-consuming and labour-intensive. Drone- and satellite-based tree biomass measurements are now being tested in CF to accelerate and simplify the estimation of tree carbon sequestration.

Do you think that adopting these new technologies can revolutionise the estimation of tree carbon sequestration in agroforestry systems?

Please rate your answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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5. **Soil salinization:** by severely altering worldwide temperature and rainfall patterns, climate change is increasing water scarcity for irrigation purposes. The reduction in water supply has caused overexploitation of available local water resources, which is finally leading to sea water infiltration in water tables of coastal areas. Soil salinization constitutes a relevant threat to SDGs 2030 Agenda (especially agroforestry productivity, biodiversity and food access) as it is already affecting 8,7% of soils at a global level with this number expected to increase up to 23% by 2100 based on realistic projections.

Do you think that an innovative solar-powered desalination system could mitigate soil salinization agroforestry systems?

Please rate your answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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6. Intensive farming is leading to a dramatic reduction in soil fertility and biodiversity. Among NbS, tree plantation in agricultural fields could increase soil biodiversity by promoting microbial communities and soil fertility using leguminous plants.

Do you think agroforestry and NbS can revert the current trend in biodiversity loss?

Please rate your answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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7. A carbon credit is a negotiable certificate corresponding to a tonne of CO₂ that is not emitted or absorbed thanks to environmental protection projects for GHG reduction or sequestration.

In agroforestry, carbon credits are generated based on the amount of CO₂ that is long-term sequestered by plants and soil. However, a standard European regulation system does still not exist.

Do you think that projects focused on regulating the system of carbon credits can support your sector?

Please rate your answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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8. The European Parliament is discussing new legislation to regulate the carbon credits market with the scope for offering auxiliary income to traditional agricultural and forestry productive activities.

Can such an opportunity incentivise the development of carbon farming activities in local agroforestry farms?

Please rate your answer on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "I do not agree" and 5 "I completely agree"

1	2	3	4	5
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Please feel free to add any suggestions on aspects important for your sector that have not been discussed in the questionnaire, whose development the project and the partners involved could contribute to.

1.1.3.2 The stakeholders questionnaire on the INNO4CFIs WEFE-Nexus approach

The partner of the WP2 - WEFE-Nexus and stakeholders analysis, under the guidance of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)- is focused on the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus, which specifically targets the mapping of existing Nexus methodologies and the assessment of Carbon needs of the involved project regions. This strategy will provide WP2 with an inventory of best practices and state-of-the-art Nexus solutions. In parallel, all this information is extremely useful for the external quality assessment of the WP9.

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming

In fact, a second external questionnaire was developed to evaluate the quality of the WEFE Nexus approach adopted by the INNO4CFIs project by reviewing 10 WEFE Nexus objectives pursued into the project. Thanks to the work of WP2, the quality team is now able to get in touch with coordinators of previous European projects addressing the WEFE Nexus approach. The analysis of the interest in the objectives of the INNO4CFIs project will provide the quality team with the impact of the project. The integral text of this first questionnaire is hereafter added.

INNO4CFIs

Questionnaire on the WEFE Nexus approach of INNO4CFIs

The EU-funded project INNO4CFIs has two main objectives:

1. Promoting reforestation practices through agroforestry systems (AFS) to increase CO₂ sequestration while promoting crucial environmental co-benefits such as sustainable freshwater production, dry-land and soil restoration and, biodiversity promotion
2. Financing highly innovative technologies promoted by SMEs located in i3-eligible countries (EU27)

The promotion of Carbon Farming (CF) practices will be the focus of the proposal, thanks to the expertise developed by the consortium through the H2020 Hydrousa project and the PRIMA Nexus project. Through the combination of the WEFE Nexus Methodology and the technological maturation of the involved technologies, the design of systemic solutions balancing the interdependencies between water, energy, food and the environment, as well as the implementation and financing of Carbon Farming projects will be ensured.

INNO4CFIs is realising agroforestry-based CF initiatives in four European Living Hubs (Tuscany, Italy; Attica, Greece; Wallonia, Belgium; Zamora, Spain). Innovative technologies will be implemented in these sites to revolutionise carbon farming practices. In particular, in the INNO4CFIs reference site of Follonica (Tuscany, Italy), the measurement of tree carbon sequestration will consist of a cross-validation of three different methods: traditional on-field destructive biomass measurements in the agroforestry plantation will validate innovative and fast drone- and satellite-based measurements. This integrated measurement strategy will be

essential to validate tree carbon sequestration data obtained by all the other European INNO4CFIs agroforestry demosites, offering a cutting-edge approach in carbon farming.

This questionnaire evaluates the quality of the WEFEX NEXUS approach adopted by INNO4CFIs by reviewing ten essential WEFEX NEXUS objectives pursued in INNO4CFIs.

All the questions have 5 possible answers:

- 1. **Very low**
- 2. **Below average**
- 3. **Average**
- 4. **Above Average**
- 5. **High**

1. **Carbon sequestration:** several past European projects on CF focused on estimating soil carbon sequestration. Traditionally, plant biomass data is obtained using destructive methods that are expensive, time-consuming and labour-intensive. INNO4CFIs will compare the efficiency of the destructive method with innovative drone- and satellite-based technologies for tree biomass quantification.

Do you think INNO4CFIs will make a step forward in the analysis of tree carbon sequestration?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

2. **Water use:** Freshwater availability is decreasing at a global level under the pressure of global change. Soil salinization is already affecting several European coastal areas by seawater infiltration in the water table, leading to a dramatic reduction in crop productivity. In the INNO4CFIs project, a solar-powered desalination system will produce freshwater from a water table that is seasonally characterised by seawater infiltration.

Do you think this new technology could be innovative for the protection of agricultural production?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

3. **Ecosystem protection and biodiversity promotion:** biodiversity is increasingly threatened by the alteration of natural ecosystems. INNO4CFIs aims to promote biodiversity through agroforestry practices that include the plantation of local European tree species such as olive, cypress, oak, willow and poplar.

Do you think planting local European tree species is an innovative way to promote biodiversity and protect the ecosystem?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

4. **Soil fertility and conservation:** agricultural intensification is causing a loss of soil fertility at the European level. INNO4CFIs aims to realise agroforestry systems that stabilise soil structure and fertility by planting local tree species.

Do you think carbon farming activities could enhance soil fertility?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

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5. **Food / By-products:** Agroforestry systems offer both woody and agricultural production.

Do you think this goal could fit carbon farming initiatives?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

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6. **Economic relevance for SME:** carbon farming – whose regulation is still under development by the European Commission – could offer additional economic profits to SMEs by the selling of carbon credits (CC). INNO4CFIs aims to enhance CF initiatives and nature-based business models in this sector.

Do you think those initiatives will be relevant in promoting the CC market?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

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7. *Social impact*: climate change is threatening worldwide crop production and human well-being by exacerbating extreme climatic events such as drought and soil salinisation. Despite numerous environmental campaigns at the European level, there is still scarce awareness of the effect of climate change on vegetation.

Can projects like INNO4CFIs contribute to raising social awareness about the effects of climate change, particularly in terms of public perception?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

8. **Scaling**: INNO4CFIs is composed of a consortium of private (SMEs) and public (research centres) actors that cooperate to revolutionise carbon farming by offering a new technological and integrated approach to attract potential stakeholders. Funded by the EU, this type of project could be of interest for a larger development through the support of regional and national European countries.

If you have knowledge on previous projects on CF and WEF NEXUS, do you think that INNO4CFIs could be replicated in similar (horizontal scaling) or bigger conditions (vertical scaling)? Please leave the answer blank in case you do not know other similar projects

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

9. **Governance, policy and regulation framework:** the EU is developing the Carbon Farming (CF) Framework, a roadmap to boost carbon farming practices across the European continent. However, the CF framework is still debated at the European Council and Parliament on what agricultural practices should be included, how to compensate farmers who join this transition and what indicators to establish for the certification of carbon sequestration.

Do you think projects like INNO4CFIs can contribute to the development of the structure of the Carbon Farming Framework?

1	2	3	4	5
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Any further comment(s) or suggestion(s)

Please indicate in the box below any additional considerations not included in the questionnaire, which might be important for your sector and to which the project and its partners could contribute

2. Conclusions

This present report shows the results of the 1st year of work on the Quality of the INNO4CFIs project. In particular, the results concern a 1st Internal evaluation of the Kick-off meeting (KoM) - held in September 2024 at the Italian Space Agency (ASI) - and a 1st

Internal Quality Assessment Questionnaire shared with the INNO4CFIs partners in February 2024 (M6).

The analysis of the results of both the questionnaires showed that the qualitative aspects of the project are clear to all the partners involved. The INNO4CFIs is on track according to the scheduled timing, targets and objectives at the beginning (concerning both Deliverables and Milestones) despite a 1st Amendment was officially approved on 17.04.2024 2024 and a 2nd Amendment has been submitted to the European Commission on 02.08.2024 .

The results have also highlighted a good degree of satisfaction of the partners regarding all the aspects involved in the project and quality management. Moreover, the results offered new suggestions and ideas on how to further improve the quality of the future INNO4CFIs meetings. Such suggestions have been taken into account by the project coordination and will be potentially developed during next months.

As next steps, the Quality team of INNO4CFIs plan to share both the above-mentioned external quality questionnaires to relevant stakeholders by the end of September 2024.

Finally, a second Internal Questionnaire will be proposed to the INNO4CFIs partners at the end of the General Assembly that will be held on 25-27 September 2024 at the CNR experimental farm of Santa Paolina (Tuscany, Italy), where the reference Agroforestry Living Hub of Follonica has been realised. During the first day of the General Assembly in Follonica, a first practical-demonstrative workshop, titled "Crediti di Carbonio ed Agroforestazione: un'opportunità di sviluppo per il territorio" will be organized. Based on a practical demonstration approach, the event aims to showcase the platforms developed and technologies deployed in the INNO4CFIs project. The workshop will be characterised by short presentations and open discussions and partly outdoors, with a visit to the innovative solar desalination system (presented by the partner involved Planet) and the newly realised agroforestry plantation, with specialists in agroforestry (CNR), carbon farming (Space4Good and AB Corporation) and experts in biodiversity and protection of water and soil resources (Planet and Treedom).